

1 **SLBP interacts with DNMT1 and EZH2.**

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6 We identified SLBP as a DNMT1 co-regulated gene, together with function in a EZH2-centric network.
7 We studied cells depleted of EZH2 to understand epigenetic control of SLBP. EZH2 controlled expression
8 of DNMT1 but not DNMT3A or DNMT3B in human cells (erythroid progenitors) and this occurred together
9 with EZH2 control of SLBP. We thus provide evidence here that the stem-loop binding protein SLBP
10 interacts with DNMT1 and EZH2 in a reaction important for transcription and gene regulation which likely
11 becomes perturbed in malignancy.

12 Citations

13 1. Battle, D.J. and Doudna, J.A., 2001. The stem-loop binding protein forms a highly stable and
14 specific complex with the 3'stem-loop of histone mRNAs. *Rna*, 7(1), pp.123-132.